

Revealing Cancer Patients' Real-World Daily Life Concerns via Large Language Models

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Abstract. After cancer diagnosis, patients often encounter uncertainties regarding the performance of daily living activities. Understanding their everyday concerns is crucial for providing quality supportive care, yet these needs often fall outside the scope of traditional health data. Using prompt engineering techniques, we employed GPT-4.1 mini to classify and categorize cancer patients' inquiries related to daily living activities from over 5,000 telephone consultation records obtained from a hospital customer service center between 2010 and 2020. Each inquiry was annotated with structured labels in the format of "Main Category (Subcategory)." To assess the reliability of the model-generated labels, 360 records were randomly sampled and manually validated, yielding an accuracy of 92.2%. The annotation process resulted in 17 main categories. The most frequently observed categories were vaccination (58.6%), diet (12.4%), supplement use (5.7%), medications (3.5%), and medical procedures (3.3%). Specifically, certain categories revealed frequent inquiries related to particular foods and lifestyle practices, including raw fish, red ginseng, mushrooms, onion juice, and sauna use. Although some inconsistencies were observed in GPT's labeling, the approach provides a scalable solution for organizing daily living inquiries or cancer patients. Future research may incorporate retrieval-augmented generation to enhance reliability and integrate patient's clinical characteristics to enable more personalized and actionable support for daily living during cancer care.

Keywords: Cancer patients; Daily living; Large language models

1 Introduction

Cancer increases patient's perceived uncertainty regarding the performance of daily living activities that are typically unproblematic under normal conditions. Thus, cancer patients frequently seek guidance on managing their daily lives after diagnosis. While cancer patients frequently experience uncertainties in managing daily living activities, such needs are often underrepresented in structured health data sources such as patient-reported outcomes (PROs) or electronic health records (EHRs). These conventional

data sources may lack the spontaneity, granularity, and breadth necessary to capture patient’s lived experiences.

To address this gap, recent studies have increasingly explored patient-generated text as a complementary data source [1]. For instance, topic modeling of chronic myeloid leukemia forums revealed persistent concerns about medication, side effects, and treatment resistance[2]. Similarly, analyses of breast cancer forums identified hidden survivorship challenges including lingering side effects and the need for long-term support[3]. While these studies offer valuable insights, they primarily focus on disease-specific issues within single cancer types. As a result, they may fail to capture the broader scope of practical, everyday inquiries that arise across diverse cancer populations. In contrast, real-world data such as telephone consultation records from hospital customer service centers can offer comprehensive insights into the day-to-day informational needs of cancer patients. However, these narrative data are largely unstructured and pose significant challenges for systematic analysis. To address these limitations, large language models (LLMs), which are capable of understanding and categorizing complex language in diverse contexts, may offer a scalable and efficient solution. Therefore, we aimed to uncover and organize patient’s real-world informational needs across multiple domains of daily life through application of LLM.

2 Methods

A total of 5,134 free-text consultation records from diverse cancer patients were analyzed. Each entry documented daily life inquiries from the incoming calls placed by cancer patients or their caregivers to the customer service center of Samsung Medical Center, South Korea, between 2010 and 2020. The study was reviewed and approved by the institutional review board of the Samsung Medical Center (SMC 2021-10-001). Our research used retrospective data containing anonymized personal information and received a waiver of informed consent from the subjects.

We first employed few-shot prompting with the GPT-4.1 mini model to generate structured multi-label annotations for each record in the format of “Main Category (Subcategory)”. The prompt included input–output examples that reflected complex and multi-intent inquiries, such as those related to vaccination eligibility, diet, and other medical procedures[4]. To assess the reliability of the LLM-generated labels, we randomly sampled 360 records using simple random sampling[5]. The sample size was selected to enable estimation of hypothetical classification accuracy (0.9) with a 3% sampling error, 95% confidence interval, and finite population correction. Human evaluation was performed to validate the GPT outputs, with binary coding (correct vs. incorrect) applied to assess accuracy. We performed descriptive analyses to identify predominant categories and created word clouds for each main category.

3 Result

Out of 5,134 consultation records, a random sample of 360 was manually validated, with 332 annotations confirmed as correct, yielding an exact-match accuracy of 92.2% for the LLM-generated labels. The annotation process identified approximately 1,950 unique subcategories organized under 17 main categories. Among the 17 identified main categories, the most frequently observed were vaccination (58.60%), diet (12.40%), supplement use (5.68%), medication (3.54%), and medical procedures (3.25%), underscoring cancer patients' predominant informational needs related to nutritional management, and self-care (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Frequency and proportion of main inquiry categories

Main category	N(%)	Main category	N(%)
Vaccination	3697(58.60)	Hygiene	131(2.08)
Diet	784(12.40)	Symptom	115(1.82)
Supplement use	358(5.68)	Wound care	36(0.57)
Medication	223(3.54)	Substance use	32(0.51)
Medical procedure	205(3.25)	Device care	24(0.38)
Physical activity	205(3.25)	Social activity	18(0.29)
Appearance	168(2.66)	Sexual & Reproductive health	14(0.22)
Daily living	148(2.35)	Clothing	9(0.14)
Travel	138(2.19)		

The most frequently reported category, vaccination, primarily included questions about eligibility for influenza, pneumococcal, and shingles vaccines, aligning with national guidelines that prioritize older adults and high-risk populations.

To highlight some distinctive aspects, raw fish was the most frequently discussed topic within the diet category (**Figure 1**). A variety of food items, such as beef tartare, eel, black goat meat, samgyetang (ginseng chicken soup), chaga mushroom tea, and persimmon were also mentioned, many of which are traditionally regarded as restorative foods in Korean culture.

In the supplement category, several types of ginsengs were noted, including red ginseng (processed), wild ginseng, and jangnoesam (semi-wild ginseng), along with other traditional health products such as sanghwang mushroom, chaga mushroom, onion juice, black garlic, and deer antler. In the medication category, herbal medicine accounted for the largest portion, indicating ongoing patient interest in alternative therapeutic approaches.

In the domain of daily living, saunas generated the highest number of questions, with jjimjilbang (Korean-style sauna) also frequently mentioned. Similarly, in the hygiene category, bathhouse use was the most commonly inquired item, subtly reflecting cultural aspects. In the appearance section, hair dyeing and perming were among the most

labeling tasks, requiring embedding-normalized text representation and manual post-hoc labeling. Second, although the selected model was appropriate for lifestyle-related concerns, other domain-specific language models may offer better performance. Third, this study was conducted using data recorded at a single hospital located in Korea. These results may not be generalizable to different countries or communities with different cultural backgrounds. Future work should consider applying retrieval-augmented generation to improve the reliability of query identification and to support tailored interventions, such as automated triage systems or chatbots, that assist with daily living activities. Furthermore, future research will focus on developing models that incorporate individual-level clinical characteristics, such as age, disease stage, and treatment status to uncover previously unrecognized unmet needs across diverse cancer populations.

5 Conclusion

This study highlights the potential of leveraging large language models to systematically capture cancer patients' everyday information needs. Our findings underscore the value of real-world inquiry data in informing scalable, patient-centered care strategies.

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